

VHR DEM Technical Note

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this technical note is to summarise the results of the integration of ten (10) VHR DEMs. Here is presented for each DEM, -the main characteristics, -the integration results in VtWeb, -a short visual analysis of the DEM with some examples and if any -the issues encountered during the integration.

1.1 References

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

RD-1. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, EDAP.REP.001, v1.2, September 2019.

1.2 Identifier syntax

In order to clearly identify each DEM, an identifier syntax has been set up. The syntax is as follow:

<Country ISO>[-<Region>]_<DEM Type>_<GSD>[_<Extra>]

Where:

- <Country ISO> Standard ISO 3166-1 Alpha-3 code of the country covered by the DEM. This tag is coded with 3 characters.
- <Region> State, region or city covered by the DEM coded on 5 characters maximum. If the DEM is national, this tag can be skipped.
- <DEM type> In the general case, should be equal to "DSM" or "DTM". Custom denominations are accepted, up to 4 characters. If the DEM type is unknown, the value "DEM" should be given.
- <GSD> An integer (1, 2, 5...) or float value (0.5, 0.25...) of the DEM resolution. If the resolution is varying, the convention <HIGHEST-GSD>-<LOWEST-GSD> should be used.
- <Extra> This extra tag may be used to differentiate between multiple DEMs of similar identifiers. If possible, any information used in this tag shouldn't be likely to change in the future. This tag is coded with less than 5 characters.

1.3 Integration method

The integration method may vary depending on the DEM properties. In general, the following steps are done:

1. DEM download from the data provider.
2. Building of tile grid distribution base on the input DEM tile.
3. Implementation of the DEM projection and perform a quality control of the localisation by comparing with an external GIS tool like QGIS.
4. Building of a quadtree either in the DEM original geometry or reprojected into the global grid at the nearest corresponding level using bilinear interpolation.
5. Add the DEM to VtWeb, which perform, if needed, the reprojection on-the-fly.

1.4 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
CRS	Coordinate Reference System
DBM	Digital Building Model
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DPM	Detailed Processing Model
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
RADAR	Radio Detection And Ranging
RGEALTI	Référentiel à Grande Echelle Altimétrique
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator
VHR	Very High Resolution
VRS	Vertical Reference System

2. FRANCE – FRA_DTM_1

2.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	<i>FRA_DTM_1</i>
Name	<i>Référentiel à Grande Echelle (RGE) Alti - 1 m</i>
Spatial coverage	<i>France (including oversea departments)</i>
GSD (m)	<i>1 m</i>
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	<i>DTM</i>
Latest version	<i>V2.0</i>
Data URL(s)	https://geoservices.ign.fr/rgealti
Raw size	<i>470 GB compressed (140 files)</i>
Data type	<i>Float (32 bits)</i>
File format	<i>ASCII</i>
EPSG	2154 for main land – various for oversea departments
CRS	<i>RGF93 v1 / Lambert-93 (for main land)</i>
VRS	<i>IGN69</i>
Tile grid	<i>1 km x 1 km tiles</i>
Pixel type (Point / Area)	<i>Point</i>
Vertical accuracy	<i>LiDAR 0.2-0.5 m, RADAR (important slopes) 7 m, photogrammetry 0.5-0.7 m</i>
Temporal coverage	-
Ancillary data	<i>SRC (source data, .tif), DST (distance to closest point used to compute height, .tif)</i>
User manual	https://geoservices.ign.fr/sites/default/files/2021-07/DC_RGEALTI_2-0.pdf
ATBD	
DPM	
Validation document(s)	
License	https://www.etalab.gouv.fr/licence-ouverte-open-licence/

2.2 Integration results

Figure 1 – France – RGE ALTI overview.

Here above is shown the result of the integration of the French DTM in VtWeb seen at several scale. The colour map range vary on every view to enhance the local range of elevation.

2.3 DEM analysis

RGE ALTI is a national DEM at 1 metre of resolution. It covers all the French territory (except some part in Bretagne). As the source mask shows here after, around 50% of the

DTM is based on LiDAR data (for the mainland). The overseas departments are far more covered by LiDAR data (near 100%), except of the French Guyana.

Figure 2 – FRA_DTM_1 – RGEALTI source mask.

Here is shown an example of the source impact on the DTM spatial resolution. We are in Champs sur Marne, with its [château](#) at the middle top of the frame. The light and dark green parts in the source mask correspond to LiDAR sources and the blue part corresponds to stereographic aerial view. The yellow part is a merging area. There is much more detail in green areas like the château gardens compared to the blue area where the highway is hardly noticeable. Here is an [hyperlook](#) display the DTM and the source mask over this area.

Figure 3 – FRA_DTM_1 – DTM and source mask close-up view ([2D view](#)).

3. ITALY – ITA-TRE_DSM_1-2_2009

3.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	ITA-TRE_DSM_1-2_2009
Name	DSM 2009
Spatial coverage	Autonomous Province of Trento
GSD (m)	1 m (type 1), 2 m (type 2 & 3)
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	DSM
Latest version	-
Data URL(s)	https://siat.provincia.tn.it/stem/
Raw size	15.8 GB compressed (1755 files)
Data type	Float (32 bits)
File format	XYZ, ASCII
EPSG	25832
CRS	ETRS89 / UTM zone 32N
VRS	http://users.south-tyrolean.net/geodetico/Geoide/Geoide_it/
Tile grid	2.02 km x 2.02 km tiles
Pixel type (Point / Area)	Area
Vertical accuracy	30 cm 2 σ (type 1), 60 cm 2 σ (type 2 & 3)
Temporal coverage	October 2006 to February 2008
Ancillary data	sunshine (.tif), orthophoto (.ECW)
User manual	http://www.territorio.provincia.tn.it/portal/server.pt/community/lidar/847/lidar/23954 (presentation of the dataset)
ATBD	-
DPM	-
Validation document(s)	-
License	http://www.territorio.provincia.tn.it/portal/server.pt/community/lidar/847/licenza_d%27uso/255622

3.2 Integration results

Figure 4 – Italy – Trentino DSM overview.

Here above is shown the result of the integration of the DSM in VtWeb seen at several scale. The colour map for the global views goes from 0 to 3,000 metres while the one for the close-up view goes from 60 to 400 metres.

Here is the tile distribution of the DSM. The red tiles correspond to the ones a 1 metres of resolution while the green tiles are the ones at 2 metres of resolution.

Figure 5 – Italy – DSM tiles distribution.

3.1 DEM analysis

This DSM is produced using LiDAR data. The structural elements are well conserved with little noise around the border as shown in the example here below over the city of Arco (Italy).

Figure 6 – ITA-TRE_DSM – City of Arco (2D view).

There are some artifacts like the following. In this example, artificial lines may be found (red arrows) where the elevation increase by around 10 metres.

Figure 7 – ITA-TRE_DSM – Artifact example (2D view).

Another example is the large water body in the south. Usually, water bodies surface is flattened to one single value, but here, one may see variation in the surface height. The colour scale goes from 60 metres to 75 metres.

Figure 8 – ITA-TRE_DSM – Water body height ([2D view](#)).

4. ITALY – ITA-TRE_DTM_1-2_2009

4.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	ITA-TRE_DTM_1-2_2009
Name	DTM 2009
Spatial coverage	Autonomous Province of Trento
GSD (m)	1 m (type 1), 2 m (type 2 & 3)
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	DTM
Latest version	-
Data URL(s)	https://siat.provincia.tn.it/stem/
Raw size	15.2 GB compressed (1755 files)
Data type	Float (32 bits)
File format	XYZ, ASCII
EPSG	25832
CRS	ETRS89 / UTM zone 32N
VRS	http://users.south-tyrolean.net/geodetico/Geoide/Geoide_it/
Tile grid	2.02 km x 2.02 km tiles
Pixel type (Point / Area)	Area
Vertical accuracy	30 cm 2 σ (type 1), 60 cm 2 σ (type 2 & 3)
Temporal coverage	October 2006 to February 2008
Ancillary data	sunshine (.tif), orthophoto (.ECW)
User manual	http://www.territorio.provincia.tn.it/portal/server.pt/community/lidar/847/lidar/23954 (presentation of the dataset)
ATBD	-
DPM	-
Validation document(s)	-
License	http://www.territorio.provincia.tn.it/portal/server.pt/community/lidar/847/licenza_d%27uso/255622

4.2 Integration results

Figure 9 – Italy – Trentino DTM overview.

Here above is shown the result of the integration of the DTM in VtWeb seen at several scale. The colour map for the global views goes from 0 to 3,000 metres while the one for the close-up view goes from 60 to 400 metres.

The tile distribution is the same as the DSM one (see 3.2).

4.1 DEM analysis

The DTM is produced by removing the surface above ground from the DSM. For example, here is the same view as the Figure 6. One may notice that all the buildings and trees from the DTM.

Figure 10 – ITA-TRE_DTM – City of Arco (2D view).

The surface above ground can be retrieved by computing a difference between the DSM and the DTM. Here is the sub surface between 0 and 20 metres.

Figure 11 – ITA-TRE – City of Arco surface above ground (2D view).

It should be noted that the artifact shown in Figure 7 is not present in the DTM as shown here after.

Figure 12 – ITA-TRE_DTM – Artifact example ([2D view](#)).

5. BRASIL – BRA-ES_DSM_2

5.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	<i>BRA-ES_DSM_2</i>
Name	<i>Modelo Digital de Elevação (MDE)</i>
Spatial coverage	<i>Brazil (Espírito Santo)</i>
GSD (m)	<i>2 m</i>
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	<i>DSM</i>
Latest version	<i>26.04.2021</i>
Data URL(s)	https://geobases.s3.es.gov.br/minio/public/MAP_ES_2012_2015/MD E/
Raw size	<i>25.4 GB (547 files)</i>
Data type	<i>Uint (16 bits)</i>
File format	<i>ERDAS Imagine Images (.img)</i>
EPSG	31984
CRS	<i>SIRGAS 2000 / UTM zone 24S</i>
VRS	https://www.isgeoid.polimi.it/Geoid/America/Brazil/brazil2010_g.html
Tile grid	<i>10 km x 10 km tiles</i>
Pixel type (Point / Area)	<i>Point (Supposed)</i>
Vertical accuracy	<i>< 2.5 m (90% of samples)</i>
Temporal coverage	<i>2012 – 2015</i>
Ancillary data	<i>input acquisitions (.img), polygon of each tile (.shp)</i>
User manual	https://geobases.s3.es.gov.br/minio/download/public/MAP_ES_2012_2015/MAP_ES_2012_2015_REFERENCIA_TECNICA.pdf
ATBD	https://geobases.s3.es.gov.br/minio/download/public/MAP_ES_2012_2015/MAP_ES_2012_2015_REFERENCIA_TECNICA.pdf
DPM	-
Validation document(s)	https://geobases.s3.es.gov.br/minio/download/public/MAP_ES_2012_2015/MAP_ES_2012_2015_REFERENCIA_TECNICA.pdf
License	https://geobases.es.gov.br/quem-somos

5.2 Integration results

Figure 13 – Brazil – Espérito Santo DSM overview.

Here above is shown the result of the integration of the DSM in VtWeb seen at several scale. The colour map for the global views (a and b) goes from 0 m to 2,000 m and the one for the close-up view (c) goes from 640 m to 750 m.

Here after is shown the input tile grid distribution. There is a total of 547 tiles. The ones in green are the tiles successfully integrated in VtWeb and the ones in orange are the tile ignored due to some issues that had occurred during the ingestion.

Figure 14 – Brazil – Espérito Santo DSM tile distribution.

5.1 DEM analysis

This DSM is provided at 2 metres of resolution. It shows several details about the above ground of the surface like forest building and so on. Unfortunately, some artifacts could be found like expose here after.

The first one is the integer data representation that quickly shows its limit. The following example displays the DSM over an urban area where steps can be seen. These steps are due to height values as integer, where the height increase by 1 meter. Here, the colour scale goes from 0 to 100 metres.

Figure 15 – BRA-ES_DSM_2 – Steps artifact over urban area (2D view).

Another artifact is a discontinuity between the input tile. Here is an example in the south part of the DSM where a nearly horizontal line of background is clearly visible.

Figure 16 – BRA-ES_DSM_2 – Tile discontinuity artifact (2D view).

5.2 Integration issues

Here are listed the issues encountered during the ingestion of the DEM. These issues are not distinct and when a tile is affected by one issue, it is often affected by the others.

5.2.1 Tile dimensions

The nominal tile size seems to be 5001 lines per 5001 columns. Some tiles have one or both dimensions lower or greater than the nominal ones. Here after is detailed the tiles dimensions.

Height \ Width	Lower	Nominal	Greater
Lower	10	6	0
Nominal	7	499	3
Greater	2	2	18

Table 1 – Tile dimension distribution.

Smaller tiles are often localised on the edge of the DEM extent and are due to small area that do not require a nominal tile dimension. But there are some of them that are smaller for no apparent reason because they are surrounded by other tiles. For example, the following snapshot shows the tile “30_767” surrounded by 8 tiles but its dimensions are lower than the nominal (first line is the tile index and second line is the width/height).

Figure 17 – Tile dimension issue example.

5.2.2 Tile localisation

For most of the tile, the name of the tile matches the upper left corner coordinates in the input CRS. For example, the tile “29_773” upper left coordinates value (290 000,

7 730 000). The easting and northing are simply divided by 10 000 which correspond in metres to the extent of the tile. This logic is confirmed by QGIS as shown here after with a snapshot of the tile extent.

Note: QGIS extend the tile bounding box by a half pixel (here 1 metre) to associate the coordinate to the pixel centre.

Information du fournisseur	
Nom	29_773
Chemin	D:\20221208_DEM_BRA-ES\DSM\29_773.img
SCR	SIRGAS_2000_UTM_Zone_24S - Projeté
Emprise	289999.000000000000000000,7719999.0000000000000000 : 300001.000000000000000000,7730001.0000000000000000
Unité	
Largeur	5001
Hauteur	5001
Type de Donnée	UInt16 - nombre entier non signé de seize bits

Figure 18 – Valid tile localisation example.

Some of the tiles do not follow this logic. These tiles are shifted and do not match with the tiling scheme. For example, the tile “36_781” should have the following upper left coordinates (360 000, 7 810 000) but according to QGIS, the coordinates are (359 999.000 122, 7 810 001.000 122), where the half pixel introduced by QGIS has been removed.

Information du fournisseur	
Nom	36_781
Chemin	D:\20221208_DEM_BRA-ES\DSM\36_781.img
SCR	SIRGAS_2000_UTM_Zone_24S - Projeté
Emprise	359998.0001220712438226,7799998.0001220712438226 : 370002.0001220712438226,7810002.0001220712438226
Unité	
Largeur	5002
Hauteur	5002
Type de Donnée	UInt16 - nombre entier non signé de seize bits

Figure 19 – Invalid tile localisation example.

5.2.3 Incoherence in overlapping area

The tiling scheme includes an overlapping of one (1) line and one (1) column with the neighbour tiles. Has shown here after, the last line of the “29_774” tile and the first line of the “23_773” tile are equal.

- 15 first samples of each line:

1204;1201;1199;1199;1198;1197;1196;1196;1198;1200;1199;1198;1198;1198;1198;
1204;1201;1199;1199;1198;1197;1196;1196;1198;1200;1199;1198;1198;1198;1198;

- 15 samples in the middle of the line:

```
1184;1180;1176;1177;1178;1178;1180;1185;1188;1190;1190;1191;1191;1191;1190;
1184;1180;1176;1177;1178;1178;1180;1185;1188;1190;1190;1191;1191;1191;1190;
```

- 15 last samples of each line:

```
1039;1037;1037;1037;1037;1035;1034;1039;1042;1045;1047;1048;1051;1053;1051;
1039;1037;1037;1037;1037;1035;1034;1039;1042;1045;1047;1048;1051;1053;1051;
```

For some tile, there is an incoherence in this overlapping area. For example, between the tile “36_782” and the tile “36_781”, the last and the first line are different as shown here below:

```
50;48;48;48;49;49;49;49;48;48;48;47;47;47;46;
12;26;24;24;24;25;25;24;23;24;24;24;24;24;23;
```

And shown here in QGIS. The darker blue line corresponds to the first line of the “36_781” tile. The lookup table goes from 1 metre to 150 metres.

Figure 20 – Tile overlapping incoherence example.

6. BRASIL – BRA-ES_DTM_2

6.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	<i>BRA-ES_DTM_2</i>
Name	<i>Modelo Digital de Terreno (MDT)</i>
Spatial coverage	<i>Brazil (Espírito Santo)</i>
GSD (m)	<i>2 m</i>
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	<i>DTM</i>
Latest version	<i>26.04.2021</i>
Data URL(s)	https://geobases.s3.es.gov.br/minio/public/MAP_ES_2012_2015/MDT/
Raw size	<i>34.9 GB (545 files)</i>
Data type	<i>Uint (16 bits)</i>
File format	<i>ERDAS Imagine Images (.img)</i>
EPSG	31984
CRS	<i>SIRGAS 2000 / UTM zone 24S</i>
VRS	https://www.isgeoid.polimi.it/Geoid/America/Brazil/brazil2010_g.html
Tile grid	<i>10 km x 10 km tiles</i>
Pixel type (Point / Area)	<i>Point (Supposed)</i>
Vertical accuracy	<i>< 2.5 m (90% of samples)</i>
Temporal coverage	<i>2012 – 2015</i>
Ancillary data	<i>input acquisitions (.img), polygon of each tile (.shp)</i>
User manual	https://geobases.s3.es.gov.br/minio/download/public/MAP_ES_2012_2015/MAP_ES_2012_2015_REFERENCIA_TECNICA.pdf
ATBD	https://geobases.s3.es.gov.br/minio/download/public/MAP_ES_2012_2015/MAP_ES_2012_2015_REFERENCIA_TECNICA.pdf
DPM	-
Validation document(s)	https://geobases.s3.es.gov.br/minio/download/public/MAP_ES_2012_2015/MAP_ES_2012_2015_REFERENCIA_TECNICA.pdf
License	https://geobases.es.gov.br/quem-somos

6.2 Integration results

This DEM has not been integrated yet due to several issues.

6.3 Integration issues

This DEM presents the same kind of issues than the DSM in section 5.

7. URUGUAY – URY_DTM_2.5_NAT

7.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	URY_DTM_2.5_NAT
Name	Modelo Digital de Terreno (MDT), cobertura nacional
Spatial coverage	Uruguay
GSD (m)	2.5 m
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	DTM
Latest version	2019
Data URL(s)	https://visualizador.ide.uy/descargas/datos/CN_Remesa_01/01_MDT/02_MDT_GeoTIFF_Resolucion_250cm/
Raw size	124 GB (6 598 files)
Data type	Float (32 bits)
File format	GeoTIFF
EPSG	31981 & 31982
CRS	SIRGAS 2000 / UTM zone 21S & SIRGAS 2000 / UTM zone 22S
VRS	EGM2008 (EPSG:3855)
Tile grid	~5 km x 5 km tiles
Pixel type (Point / Area)	Point
Vertical accuracy	1.5 m (95% of confidence)
Temporal coverage	2017 – 2018
Ancillary data	input acquisitions (.tiff, .jpg) estimated heights areas (.shp), breaklines (.dxf), grid (.shp)
User manual	https://visualizador.ide.uy/descargas/datos/00_Instructivo_para_descargas_1.0.pdf
ATBD	https://visualizador.ide.uy/descargas/datos/Documentos_IDE/Proyecto_de_produccion_y_control_de_informacion_geografica/Informe_Final_Topocart.pdf
DPM	-
Validation document(s)	https://visualizador.ide.uy/descargas/datos/Documentos_IDE/Proyecto_de_produccion_y_control_de_informacion_geografica/Informe_Final_Topocart.pdf
License	https://www.gub.uy/agencia-gobierno-electronico-sociedad-informacion-conocimiento/sites/agencia-gobierno-electronico-sociedad-informacion-conocimiento/files/documentos/publicaciones/licencia_de_datos_abiertos_0.pdf

7.2 Integration results

Figure 21 – Uruguay – National DTM overview.

Here above is shown the result of the integration of the DTM in VtWeb seen at several scale. The colour map for the global views (a and b) goes from 0 m to 500 m and the one for the close-up view (c) goes from 1.4 m to 60 m.

On the right is shown the tile distribution of the DTM. Both colours, red and yellow, correspond to the associated UTM zone, respectively 21S and 22S.

Figure 22 – Uruguay – Tile distribution.

7.3 DEM analysis

No major artifact has been found.

Here after is shown some notable places like the four dams of Uruguay. On the following snapshots, there is on the left the DTM and on the right the slope computed from the DTM.

Figure 23 – URY_DTM_2.5_NAT – Dams of Uruguay (2D view).

7.4 Integration issues

No major issues were encountered during the integration. One thing should be noted, each tile of the DTM was reprojected separately in the output UTM projection which led to discontinuity between tiles.

Here after is shown a close-up view of the tile distribution. It illustrates the discontinuity between tile footprint.

Figure 24 – Uruguay – Tile distribution close-up view.

The DTM has been reprojected in EPSG:4326 to simplify the integration in VtWeb. The output resolution is approximately 0.0077 arcsecond (around 2.3886 m at equator) and the interpolation used was “bilinear”.

8. URUGUAY – URY_DTM_1_URB

8.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	URY_DTM_1_URB
Name	Modelo Digital de Terreno (MDT), cobertura urbana
Spatial coverage	Uruguay (urban only, near Montevideo)
GSD (m)	1 m
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	DTM
Latest version	2019
Data URL(s)	https://visualizador.ide.uy/descargas/datos/CU_Remesa_01/01_MDT_MDS/01_Ciudad_MVD/04_MDT_GeoTIFF_Resolucion_100cm/
Raw size	7 GB (2765 files)
Data type	Float (32 bits)
File format	GeoTIFF
EPSG	31981 & 31982
CRS	SIRGAS 2000 / UTM zone 21S & SIRGAS 2000 / UTM zone 22S
VRS	EGM2008 (EPSG:3855)
Tile grid	~1 km x 1 km tiles
Pixel type (Point / Area)	Point
Vertical accuracy	0.3 m (95% of confidence)
Temporal coverage	2017 – 2018
Ancillary data	estimated heights areas (.shp), breaklines (.dxf), grid (.shp)
User manual	https://visualizador.ide.uy/descargas/datos/00_Instructivo_para_descargas_1.0.pdf
ATBD	https://visualizador.ide.uy/descargas/datos/Documentos_IDE/Proyecto_de_produccion_y_control_de_informacion_geografica/Informe_Final_Topocart.pdf
DPM	-
Validation document(s)	https://visualizador.ide.uy/descargas/datos/Documentos_IDE/Proyecto_de_produccion_y_control_de_informacion_geografica/Informe_Final_Topocart.pdf
License	https://www.gub.uy/agencia-gobierno-electronico-sociedad-informacion-conocimiento/sites/agencia-gobierno-electronico-sociedad-informacion-conocimiento/files/documentos/publicaciones/licencia_de_datos_abiertos_0.pdf

8.2 Integration results

Figure 25 – Uruguay – Urban DTM overview.

Here above is shown the result of the integration of the DTM in VtWeb seen at several scale. The colour map for the global views (a and b) goes from 0 m to 200 m and the one for the close-up view (c) goes from 0 m to 20 m.

On the right is shown the tile distribution of the DTM. Both colours, red and yellow, correspond to the associated UTM zone, respectively 21S and 22S. Tiles are mostly localised on the south of Uruguay.

Figure 26 – Uruguay – Tile distribution.

8.3 DEM analysis

This DTM has more details in the urban areas not only because of the spatial resolution increase (from 2.5 metres for the national coverage to 1 metre for the urban coverage) but also because the house blocs are less flattened. The following example shows a small part of Montevideo, capital of Uruguay, from the urban and the national DTM.

Figure 27 – URY_DTM_1_URB – Comparison of the urban and national DEM ([2D view](#)).

8.4 Integration issues

No major issues were encountered during the integration of this DTM. As for the National coverage, the DTM has been reprojected into one common grid due to the individual projection of each tiles (see 7.4).

9. UNITED KINGDOM – GBR-ENG_DTM_1

9.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	GBR-ENG_DTM_1
Name	National LiDAR Programme DTM
Spatial coverage	England
GSD (m)	1 m
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	DTM
Latest version	-
Data URL(s)	https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/000734e9-15bd-4768-80c8-f37235591efb
Raw size	328 GB compressed (6 156 files)
Data type	Float (32 bits)
File format	GeoTIFF
EPSG	27700
CRS	OSGB36 British National Grid (Transverse Mercator)
VRS	Ordnance Survey Newlyn (OSSTN'15/OSGM'15)
Tile grid	5 km x 5 km tiles
Pixel type (Point / Area)	Area
Vertical accuracy	+/- 15cm RMSE (LiDAR data)
Temporal coverage	2016 to 2022
Ancillary data	Intensity Surface Model, Vegetation Object Model (VOM), Point Cloud
User manual	https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/668881ad-4f8f-42bd-b835-89acf0269496
ATBD	-
DPM	-
Validation document(s)	-
License	https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/668881ad-4f8f-42bd-b835-89acf0269496

9.2 Integration results

Figure 28 – United Kingdom – DTM overview.

Here above is shown the result of the integration of the DTM in VtWeb seen at several scale. The colour map for the global views (a and b) goes from 0 m to 1,000 m and the one for the close-up view (c) goes from 0 m to 40 m.

9.3 DEM analysis

The DTM covers most of the England area except for a small part on the north as shown here after. There are also smaller holes here and there.

Figure 29 – GBR-ENG_DTM_1 – DTM coverage and hole (2D view).

Here is some zoomed views of open-pit quarries spotted at low-scale. It illustrates the level of details of this DEM. The colour scale goes from -50 metres to 150 metres.

Figure 30 – GBR-ENG_DTM_1 – Open-pit quarries viewed in 2D (left) and 3D (right) [\(2D view\)](#).

9.4 Integration issues

The major issue for the integration of this DEM was the projection. The DEM is in a Transverse Mercator projection based on the Airy1830 (EPSG:27700). This implies to: -convert the EPSG:4326 coordinates to the Airy1830 ellipsoid, -compute the Transverse Mercator projection coordinates from the Airy1830 ones and -compute the image coordinates from the Transverse Mercator projection ones.

10. UNITED KINGDOM – GBR-ENG_DSMF_1

10.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	GBR-ENG_DSMF_1
Name	National LiDAR Programme First Return DSM
Spatial coverage	England
GSD (m)	1 m
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	DSM
Latest version	-
Data URL(s)	https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/000734e9-15bd-4768-80c8-f37235591efb
Raw size	342 GB compressed (6 156 files)
Data type	Float (32 bits)
File format	GeoTIFF
EPSG	27700
CRS	OSGB36 British National Grid (Transverse Mercator)
VRS	Ordnance Survey Newlyn (OSSTN'15/OSGM'15)
Tile grid	5 km x 5 km tiles
Pixel type (Point / Area)	Area
Vertical accuracy	+/- 15cm RMSE (LiDAR data)
Temporal coverage	2016 to 2022
Ancillary data	Intensity Surface Model, Vegetation Object Model (VOM), Point Cloud
User manual	https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/668881ad-4f8f-42bd-b835-89acf0269496
ATBD	-
DPM	-
Validation document(s)	-
License	https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/668881ad-4f8f-42bd-b835-89acf0269496

10.2 Integration results

Figure 31 – United Kingdom – DSMF overview.

Here above is shown the result of the integration of the DSMF in VtWeb seen at several scale. The colour map for the global views (a and b) goes from 0 m to 1 000 m and the one for the close-up view (c) goes from 0 m to 40 m.

10.3 DEM analysis

The DSMF is a Digital Surface Model computed from the first return of the LiDAR points cloud. It describes the top surface, showing building, vegetation, ... Compared to the DTM, there are a lot more of small missing part scattered all over the coverage.

Here is a close-up view of London, where the London Bridge and the Tower of London are visible. The colour scale goes from 0 metre to 100 metres. One may notice the high level

of details as well as the fact that the river has not been post processed in order to be flattened.

Figure 32 – GBR-ENG_DSMF_1 – View of the inner London ([2D view](#)).

It is possible to compute the difference between the DSMF and the DTM to obtain the surface above ground as follow.

Figure 33 – GBR-ENG_DSMF_1 – Surface above ground ([2D view](#)).

10.4 Integration issues

This DSM has the same issues as the DTM (see 9.4).

11. UNITED KINGDOM – GBR-ENG_DSM_1

11.1 Input DEM features

Product Details	
Identifier	GBR-ENG_DSM_1
Name	National LiDAR Programme DSM
Spatial coverage	England
GSD (m)	1 m
Type (DTM/DSM/DBM/DEM)	DSM
Latest version	-
Data URL(s)	https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/000734e9-15bd-4768-80c8-f37235591efb
Raw size	335 GB compressed (6 156 files)
Data type	Float (32 bits)
File format	GeoTIFF
EPSG	27700
CRS	OSGB36 British National Grid (Transverse Mercator)
VRS	Ordnance Survey Newlyn (OSSTN'15/OSGM'15)
Tile grid	5 km x 5 km tiles
Pixel type (Point / Area)	Area
Vertical accuracy	+/- 15cm RMSE (LiDAR data)
Temporal coverage	2016 to 2022
Ancillary data	Intensity Surface Model, Vegetation Object Model (VOM), Point Cloud
User manual	https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/668881ad-4f8f-42bd-b835-89acf0269496
ATBD	-
DPM	-
Validation document(s)	-
License	https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/668881ad-4f8f-42bd-b835-89acf0269496

11.2 Integration results

Figure 34 – United Kingdom – DSM overview.

Here above is shown the result of the integration of the DSM in VtWeb seen at several scale. The colour map for the global views (a and b) goes from 0 m to 1,000 m and the one for the close-up view (c) goes from 0 m to 40 m.

11.3 DEM analysis

This DSM corresponds to a surface between the DTM and the DSMF. If we zoom on the same area as Figure 32, one may see that the building are still visible where the tree are less visible in the DSM than in the DSMF.

Figure 35 – GBR-ENG_DSM_1 – View of the inner London (2D view).

By computing the difference between the DSMF and the DTM, one may notice that the main differences are located on vegetated area or around the building. It should be not that the DSMF is not always above the DSM as we can see some blue dot in the Figure 36.

Figure 36 – GBR-ENG_DSM_1 – Difference between DSMF and DSM (2D view).

11.4 Integration issues

This DSM has the same issues as the DTM (see 9.4).

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